

Equilibrium studies of ternary chelates of some divalent metal ions with cephalosporins and α -alanine

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The formation of bioligand chelates of some divalent metal ions Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd and Mg with cephaloridine as primary ligand (L) and α -alanine as the secondary ligand (A) has been carried out pH-metrically at 25 and 35° and at constant ionic strength, $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄). The stability constants follow the order : Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} > Co^{II} > Ni^{II} > Cd^{II} > Mg^{II} > Mn^{II}. The log K values are less negative than -0.6, suggesting favoured formation of ternary complexes. Stability constants have been evaluated and discussed in terms of the basicity of the ligand, statistical and stereochemical phenomenon and compared with that of cephalixin drug.

Cephaloridine and cephalixin are the wide spectrum antibiotics of β -lactam cephalosporin group. The mode of action of cephalosporins has been explained by interference with the synthesis of the protein layers of the cell wall. They are supposed to attack the peptide bond of the transpeptidase enzyme at two places viz. D-ala and D-ala-D-ala (ala = alanine). The study of complexation equilibria of metal ion with the fragments of the enzyme system involved in the presence of the antibiotic drug is useful in elucidating the mechanism of action of the drug¹. Though considerable work has been done on the complexes of penicillin and cephalosporin drugs with a number of cations²⁻⁴, a scanty work appears to have been done in the area of mixed ligand complexes involving fragments of enzyme systems. Here we report the results of the study of metal-cephaloridine-alanine equilibria in solution using Irving-Rossotti method⁵.

Results and Discussion

Conductometric studies of the metal-drug and metal-alanine equilibria in solution⁶ indicate formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal-drug or metal-alanine complexes respectively. Addition of third molecule of the ligand did not take place probably due to steric hindrance of the bulky ligand molecules²⁻⁴.

The pH-titration curves of cephaloridine and alanine lie before the acid curve (Fig. 1), indicating that in acidic solutions each ligand molecule is in association with one equivalent of proton. This proton should be attached to the lone-pair of electrons present on the nitrogen of the β -lactam thiazolidine ring in case of cephalixin and on the nitrogen of amino group in case of alanine². This corresponds to two successive deprotonation steps of the protonated ligands.

Eqn. (1) corresponds to the ionisation of the carboxyl group of the ligands, while eqn. (2) denotes deprotonation of the proton attached to the nitrogen atom. The former

Fig. 1. pH titration curves, cephalo-ala system (A) acid; (B) (A) + cephalo; (C) (A) + ala, (D) (B) + M, (E) (C) + M, (F) (B) + ala, (G) (F) + M

takes place in the pH range 3.5-5 and the later in pH 6.5-10. Earlier reports also indicate similar steps of deprotonation²⁻⁴.

The experimental titration curves (Fig. 1) reveal that

formation of different M^{II} : drug binary complexes takes place below pH 6.4. This is clear from the appeared divergence of each of the 1 : 1 binary M^{II} drug titration curve from that of the corresponding free drug curve in the range of pH 5–8, beyond this hydrolysis of the complexes leads to the formation of hydroxo-complex species.

Careful examination of titration curves reveals that the 1 : 1 : 1 mixed ligand complexes are formed at pH values higher than those corresponding to the formation of the binary complexes of the drug in the stepwise manner similar to the formation of 1 : 2 binary complexes :

where ${}^+HL^-$ is the protonated cephaloridine ion and HAH^+ the protonated alanine molecule.

The conductometric titrations of the metal-drug 1 : 1 solution with alanine solution also indicate formation of metal : drug alanine 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complex. This found further conformation in λ_{max} for the ternary complex as compared to that of the metal-drug and metal-alanine binary complexes. It may be noted here that high intensity bands are obtained in UV region in the case of both the ligands which generally obscure other frequencies in their metal complexes. Thus the high intensity bands in cephaloridine and its complexes were obtained at ≈ 238 and ≈ 192 nm, which may be assigned to $\pi-\pi$ and $n-\sigma^*$ transitions due to benzene and C=O of amido and carboxylic chromophores⁷. Cephalixin and its complexes registered high intensity bands at ≈ 260 and ≈ 190 nm for the same transitions. However, one weak band is also obtained in the visible region in every case.

The Mn^{II} -cephalo (cephaloridine) and Mn^{II} -ceph (cephalexin) binary complexes gave bands at ≈ 21.0 and ≈ 18.35 kK, respectively, which shifted to 21.8 and 18.50 kK in the ternary complexes Mn^{II} -cephalo-ala and Mn^{II} -ceph-ala, respectively. These bands may be assigned to ${}^2T_{2g}(G) \rightarrow {}^2E_g(G)$ and ${}^2T_{2g}(I) \rightarrow {}^6A_{1g}(I)$ transitions, respectively, in octahedral stereochemistry⁸. The Co^{II} -cephalo and Co^{II} -ceph binary complexes registered bands at ≈ 19.1 and ≈ 17.24 kK, respectively, which in the ternary complexes Co^{II} -cephalo-ala and Co^{II} -ceph-ala shifted to ≈ 20.0 and ≈ 17.7 kK for ${}^2E_g(G) \rightarrow {}^2T_{1g}(G)$ and ${}^2E_g(G) \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}(G)$ transitions, respectively, in octahedral stereochemistry⁹. The binary complexes Ni^{II} -cephalo and Ni^{II} -ceph gave bands at ≈ 20.8 and ≈ 15.96 kK, respectively. These bands shifted to ≈ 20.0 and 16.0 kK in ternary complexes Ni^{II} -cephalo-ala and Ni^{II} -ceph-ala corresponding to transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$, respectively, in octahedral field⁹. Similarly, the bands at

≈ 19.0 and 12.4 kK in the Cu^{II} -cephalo and Cu^{II} -ceph binary complexes, respectively, shifted to ≈ 19.65 and ≈ 12.82 kK in the corresponding ternary complexes Cu^{II} -cephalo-ala and Cu^{II} -ceph-ala due to the transitions ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transitions in distorted octahedral stereochemistry¹⁰.

It may be noted that the ternary complexes, MLA are comparatively more stable than the corresponding 1 : 2 binary complexes of the drugs; but they have low stability compared to the binary complexes, i.e. $K_{ML}^M > K_{MLA}^{ML}$, due to statistical, steric and electrostatic factors. $\Delta \log K$ values should be negative¹¹ qualifying favoured formation of ternary complex¹², compared to that of the 1 : 2 binary (ML_2) complexes (Table 1).

Table 1. Stability constants of M^{II} -cephalo-ala system*

Metal	Temp	$\log K_{ML}^M$	$\log K_{ML_2}^{ML}$	$\log K_{MLA}^{ML}$	$\Delta \log K$
Mg^{II}	25 ^o	4.48	2.65	4.16	
	35 ^o	4.28	2.54	3.76	-0.52
Mn^{II}	25 ^o	4.22	2.65	3.89	
	35 ^o	3.75	2.00	3.39	-0.36
Co^{II}	25 ^o	5.60	3.60	4.87	
	35 ^o	5.10	3.31	4.56	-0.54
Ni^{II}	25 ^o	5.20	3.50	5.08	
	35 ^o	4.90	3.21	4.46	-0.44
Cu^{II}	25 ^o	6.95	3.70	6.32	
	35 ^o	6.30	3.60	-5.66	-0.64
Zn^{II}	25 ^o	5.80	3.55	5.22	
	35 ^o	5.50	3.51	5.12	-0.38
Cd^{II}	25 ^o	4.92	3.48	4.58	
	35 ^o	4.80	3.00	4.34	-0.46
H	25 ^o	7.87	3.25		
	35 ^o	7.25	2.97		

*Limit of error = $\pm (0.02-0.08)$

The stability order with reference to metal ions, follow the Irving-Williams order in general. The only exception is Ni^{II} , forming the least stable complexes amongst Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} , and even the stability of the Co^{II} complex is greater than the Ni^{II} complex. Such exception have also been observed earlier by Sigel and others¹³. This shows that the mixed complexes containing Ni^{II} are less favoured than those with Co^{II} , Cu^{II} or Zn^{II} , and probably this quality of Ni^{II} is one of the reasons why this metal ion rarely occurs in biological systems. The order obtained in the present investigation is : $Mn^{II} < Mg^{II} < Cd^{II} < Ni^{II} < Co^{II} < Zn^{II} < Cu^{II}$. However, these complexes are less stable than that of cephalixin complexes⁴.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Pure sample of cephaloridine (Lupin Pharma Ltd., India) was used.

The preparation and standardisation of the metal ions and the ligand solutions, and the experimental details are the same as reported earlier².

Stoichiometry of the complexes was ascertained by conductometry titrations. The Calvin Bjerrum's pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁵ was applied to determine formation constants at 25 and 35° and 0.1 M (NaClO₄) ionic strength. For pH titrations the following thermostated mixtures were titrated with a carbonate free 0.1 M NaOH solution: (a) 10 ml 0.04 M HClO₄, (b) mixture (a) + 5 ml 0.004 M cephaloridine, (c) mixture (a) + 5 ml 0.004 M alanine, (d) mixture (b) + 10 ml 0.002 M metal, (e) mixture (c) + 10 ml 0.002 M metal, (f) mixture (b) + 5 ml 0.004 M alanine, (g) mixture (f) + 10 ml 0.002 M metal. The ionic strength of the above solutions was maintained to 0.1 by adding required quantity of 1.0 M NaClO₄ solution and the total volume of the solution was 50 ml.

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